

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

DEMOGRAPHIC SITUATION IN AZERBAIJAN IN THE MIDDLE AGES IN AZERBAIJANI HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE SECOND HALF OF THE XX CENTURY - THE BEGINNING OF THE XXI CENTURY

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Abstract

In the Azerbaijani historiography of the second half of the 20th century, we can observe a limited number of research works on the demographic situation in the Middle Ages, closely related to the socio-political conditions, restrictions, prohibitions and ideological requirements of that time (namely Soviet period). At that time, the strict control over the social sciences, and mainly the fact that our historical achievements were often ignored or distorted, caused serious obstacles to the scientific and objective coverage of the history of Azerbaijan. However, despite the existing numerous difficulties, a number of valuable research works on the medieval demographic circumstance were published in Azerbaijani historiography during that period. After Azerbaijan regained its independence, with the elimination of ideological shackles and restrictions on historical science, especially at the beginning of the XXI century, more reliable, scientific-objective research works on the medieval period, including the urban population of the said period, appeared in Azerbaijani historiography. As a whole, in the second half of the 20th century - at the beginning of the 21st century, Z. Bunyadov, M. Sharifli, A. Alizade, J. Ibrahimov, Y. Mahmudov, K. Shukurov and many other Azerbaijani historians focused on various stages of the medieval period, including those that took place in our medieval cities. They managed to investigate the impact of socio-political and economic events, population settlement, natural and mechanical growth of population, and general population growth on a scientific-objective level and describe the historical demographic environment in detail.

Keywords: Azerbaijani historiography, population settlement, population growth, the Middle Ages, the population of Azerbaijan, historical demography.

The location of Azerbaijan in a favorable geo-strategic position, including rich natural resources, which are among the first production areas and have wide opportunities for the development of livestock and agriculture, which create a reliable basis for abundant food supply, have led people to settle and live in this territory. Starting from the Late Bronze Age, the transformation of trade into an independent field, the transit important roads on which cities will be formed through the territory of Azerbaijan gave impetus to the further strengthening of the settlement process here. It is these factors that give Azerbaijani scientists the opportunity to substantiate with concrete facts the idea that the history of Azerbaijani cities, their foundation and the settlement of the population in them actually dates back to more ancient times than to the Middle Ages. For example, in the book "Gabala" written by I. Aliyev and F. Gadirov, the authors disagree with the fact that the city of Gabala was built during the Sassanid king Kavad I: "The remains of the ancient caravan route passing through Gabala prove that the city of Gabala had extensive trade relations with many countries of the West and East, including the provinces of the Roman, Parthian and Sasanian empires, in the 3rd century BC – 3rd century AD". [4, p. 12]. The authors also refer to the discovery of a large number of money hoards minted here with the names of Alexander the Great, Seleucid, Greco-Bactrian, Parthian kings, Roman emperors, and Sassanid kings: "However, as can be seen from the above information, Gabala existed long before Kavad I. Therefore, we cannot agree with the idea that the city was founded by this Iranian king"

[4, p. 13]. Azerbaijani historian M. Sharifli approaches the issue of the date of establishment of the city of Gabala from the same position: "Gabala is one of the ancient cities of Albania. The famous Roman scientist Claudius Ptolemy mentioned the name of Gabala when he listed the names of Albanian cities and towns. Referring to this fact, M. Sharifli disagrees with opinion of Arab historian Yaqut al-Hamavi who writes: "Gabala is an ancient city, it was built by King Kavad near Darband" and Sharifli writes: "As it can be seen from this information, Gabala existed at the beginning of Christ" [8, p. 293].

In the book "Abbreviation of "Monuments" and the miracles of the mighty king" written at the beginning of the 15th century by Abdurrashid al-Bakuvi, a well-known scientist of the Middle Ages, whose father was born in Baku, was given extremely valuable information about the city and other settlements of Azerbaijan. It should be noted that Z. Bunyadov, who translated this work of the outstanding scientist A. Bakuvi from Arabic, which was first published in the Azerbaijani language in 1992, and wrote a preface and comments to it: "... especially accurate information about Baku, this there is great truth in the opinion that it is a sign of a good, perhaps personal acquaintance with the country". Because, in the words of Z. Bunyadov, only a person who lives in Baku, or in any case is in the homeland of his horse, can give such extensive and interesting information about the city that he saw, loved, and was native to him [2, p.3]. However, another point that attracts attention in the said work is the information provided by the author on the medieval urban planning culture of

Azerbaijan, especially the population settlement in cities, which is an important demographic process. Abdurrashid al-Bakuvi presented the construction of cities in natural-geographically favorable areas as the will of God: "God inspired people to build walls, ditches and fences. Thus, cities, villages and settlements were formed. And the kings of the past, with the advice of wise men, chose for themselves the best province in the country, the best place in this province, and in this place, on the coast of the sea and the river, in the mountains and protected from the north wind" [2, p.9]. From this, it becomes clear that the author emphasizes the dependence of population settlement in medieval cities not only on natural, but also on anthropogenic factors, thus it is an extremely good introduction to the culture of urban planning. After all, in the Middle Ages, when wars, famines, droughts, and other mass epidemics often occurred, in order to protect against sudden enemy attacks, both strong defensive walls and preventive measures had to be taken to prevent the population from gathering densely during the time of scary, rapidly spreading diseases, and the necessary conditions had to be taken into account in advance: "They built a strong wall around the city, opened many doors and gates inside the walls so that people would not gather during commuting" [2, p.9].

All important political events and messes that took place in Azerbaijani history had a serious impact on demographic processes. Starting from the 7th century: "Military operations conducted in the historical territory of Azerbaijan in connection with the Arab invasion caused great damage to cities and villages. The Arabs, who captured many cities in the Middle East relatively easily, "without serious damage to the economy", met with sharp resistance in most of the cities of Azerbaijan. As a result of the great damage to the urban economy, a number of cities declined" [6, p. 105-106]. But later, the Arabs changed the direction of the main trade route of Byzantium through the Black Sea and directed it to the shores of the East-Caspian Sea, which led to the revival of Azerbaijani cities. The names of many cities, villages and settlements of Azerbaijan are mentioned in Arabic sources, especially in works of Arabic authors of the IX and X centuries – Ibn Khordadbeh, Al Istakhri, al-Muqaddasi, etc.

Because of the weakening of the Arab caliphate in the second half of the 9th century, strong feudal dynasties such as the Sajis, Salaris, Shirvanshahs, Shaddads, and Ravvadis were formed in the territory of Azerbaijan, and the lands of the Azerbaijan were reunited within a single state. This meant, first of all, the increase of the country's defence capability, the resolute prevention of destructive attacks from abroad, and the achievement of political stability necessary for the natural growth and settlement of population. This also meant: "The development of cities, the high progress of urban life, including the revival of relations with the Middle East region" [11, p.51].

This conclusion can be reached when considering the research works on medieval cities in the historiography of Azerbaijan in the second half of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century. So, in the research works of our historical scholars regarding the

mentioned problem, we witness the amazingly high level of settlement in the medieval cities of Azerbaijan. The famous historian A. Alizadeh in his famous work "Socio-economic and political history of Azerbaijan in the XIII-XIV centuries" referring to the work of the anonymous author of the 11th century "Ajaib ad-dunya" mentioned that the cities of Azerbaijan were well-developed, abundantly equipped with all kinds of means of life, and therefore good for populated settlements.

Azerbaijani historians review almost all existing local and foreign sources related to the establishment of cities through a comparative analysis, trying not to ignore the objective factors that determine the high level of settlement. In his work "Journey to the Past of Karabakh", R. Goyushov expresses his attitude to the questions still waiting to be answered regarding the establishment of the city of Barda: "When and by whom was founded Barda, one of the most magnificent cities of the ancient East throughout the Middle Ages? There is no clear answer to this question yet". Regarding the establishment of the city, the author agrees with the opinion of the 7th century historian M. Kaghankatvatsi that it was built by Vache, the Albanian ruler of Barda, during the reign of the Sasanian ruler Peroz (459-484) with the information of another source: "Persian historian Hamdullah Qazvini takes the history of the construction of the city to an earlier date. According to him, this city was first built by Alexander the Great, and later expanded by the Sassanid ruler Kavad" [5, p.38]. However, R. Goyushov expresses his critical attitude to the mentioned source and writes: "Of course, this idea is wrong. Because as a result of historical facts, it has been definitively established that Alexander the Great never visited Azerbaijan". R. Goyushov tried to compare almost all the available sources related to the construction of the city, and this time he turned his attention to the Arab authors: "The opinion of the Arab author al-Balazuri about the history of the construction of the city attracts more attention". He wrote that "Sasanian ruler Kavad (484-531) built Barda, the capital of the whole country, in Arran" [5, p.38].

The author does not agree with the source's information this time, he rightly believes that the city of Barda already existed when the Sassanids moved the country's capital to Barda. On the other hand, the author insists on the fact that a rich cultural layer of the ancient period was discovered in Barda as a result of archaeological excavations, and the fact that the city was allegedly built by Muhammad Maraghi during the time of Abdul Malik ibn Marwan (685-705) or by people named Abdul Aziz ibn Hatam in 704, strongly states that it has nothing to do with historical reality. Thus, the researcher analyzes the information in the written sources about the history of the construction of the said city in a comparative way with the examples of pre-writing archeological material culture, and concludes that the city of Barda is a great city and a place of residence with a dense population since ancient times [5, p. 39]. This clearly shows that the culture of medieval urban planning in Azerbaijan was formed not only in the time period to which it belongs, but in historical periods older than itself. Or, may be in Azerbaijan, since the

Middle Bronze Age, that is, from the time when the first cities appeared, the process of settlement has continued uninterruptedly in the same residential areas.

M. Sharifli writes about the construction of numerous Azerbaijani cities such as Barda, Shamakhi, Shabran, Darband, Gorkara, Muscat, Beylagan, Gabala, etc. during the time of the Sassanid kings, especially Anushirvan and notes that these cities already existed in the III-VII centuries [8, p.291].

It is impossible not to mention here Davud Akhundov's views on the history of Baku, the famous architect of Azerbaijan. According to him, the age of the famous Maiden Tower in Baku belongs not to the XII century, but to the VIII-VII centuries BC [10, p.98]. D. Akhundov agrees with the opinion of a number of researchers that one of the ancient names of Baku is Khunsar or Khunzar, which is at least three to four thousand years old [10, p.73]. He believes that there were already oil fields in Absheron in the VIII-VII centuries BC, whose history dates back to the II, or perhaps the III millennia. Referring to this fact, the author here refers the history of the settlement process to the II-III millennia: "According to the results obtained as a result of archaeological excavations, the vast majority of settlements in Absheron belong to the II-III millennia". [10, p. 98].

Taking into account all these factors, the author concludes that there is a high level of settlement in the medieval cities of Azerbaijan. R. Goyushov, in his comments about Barda, specifically emphasizes the fact that the city was densely populated in the mentioned period: "According to the sources, the length of Barda city was 5-6 km in the VII-IX centuries, and strong fortress walls were built around it. These castle walls with large iron gates were so magnificent that in times of serious danger, not only the population of the city itself, but also the population of the entire surrounding area sought refuge here to protect themselves from the enemy. At that time, more than 100 thousand people lived in Barda" [5, p. 39]. From the cited quotation, it is known that one of the reasons for the dense population of the city was that Barda had strong defensive walls to protect against sudden or continuous enemy attacks and long-lasting sieges in the Middle Ages, when wars often took place. However, only this factor could not be the only reason for the high level of settlement in medieval cities.

In the mentioned period, the dense population of the cities demanded the establishment of sanitary rules and the observance of personal hygiene rules to prevent epidemics that could result in mass casualties at any time. On the other hand, dense population necessitated the development of urban infrastructure. Therefore, medieval cities had many public buildings, including commercial facilities: "The city (Barda – A.M.) had 4 large bazaars, special handicraft quarters, several baths and many religious and public buildings built in the style of Eastern architecture". Abdurrashid al-Bakuvi, whom we mentioned above, also talked about big cities in his mentioned work: "In the best neighborhoods of the cities, they set aside space for the judges, regular and Friday mosques, bazaars, caravansaras and baths. They kept other places for themselves" [2, p.9].

Z. Bunyadov writes that the establishment of the Azerbaijani Atabeg state in the XI century also had a positive effect on the development of the medieval cities of Azerbaijan: "The reign of the Azerbaijani Atabegs is the century of the prosperity of urban life in the country. During this period, many cities of Azerbaijan were large settlements that collected all types of medieval arts" [3, p.185].

The settlement of the population in the medieval towns and villages of Azerbaijan and the provision of peaceful living worried the wise statesmen. According to Khaja Nizam al-Mulk Hasan ibn Ali, who was the vizier (high-ranking political advisor or minister – A.M.) of one of the Seljuk sultans, Alp Arslan, and his son Malikshah, who gained great fame for his high management skills and took over almost all the authority of the magnificent Seljuk state, which included several countries, for thirty years, the Shah who ruled the state must implement the most necessary measures to ensure peaceful order, comfortable living and settlement of the population. In other words, according to Nizam al-Mulk, the Shah should be engaged in the improvement of the world, he should build dams, dig ditches, build bridges over large rivers, beautify villages, erect forts, build new cities, build tall buildings, beautiful mansions, and order the establishment of caravansary on major avenues (caravan roads) [6, p.107]. Nizam al-Mulk paid a lot of attention to the cultural attitude of the officials towards the people: "The rulers who have iqta should know that their rights over the subjects are only to receive the taxes entrusted to them from the subjects with pleasure. If they bought it, their lives, goods, wives and children should be safe. It should not be touched on the doorsteps. The rulers should not be an obstacle on their way".

Moreover, in order for the population not to leave the populated areas, Nizam al-Mulk wrote to the officials advising them that if one of the subjects is poor and needs an ox or a grain, it is necessary to lend him a hand and lighten his burden, so that he stays in place, leaves his home, and does not go abroad to the provinces. If something is taken from the vassal, it must be returned immediately and given to the vassal.

It is for this reason that in the mentioned period, cities traditionally flourished again as centers of art and trade, and there was an amazing increase in the natural growth of the population: "Cities played the role of the center of both internal and external trade. If we take into account that 100,000 or more people live in Nakhchivan, Beylagan, Tabriz and Shamakhi, and up to half a million people live in Ganja, then it is clear that this development was because of the increase in the number of people working in the highly developed multi-field handicraft industry, which required a population flow from rural areas to cities. [3, p. 185]. This approach of Azerbaijani prominent historian and orientalist Z. Bunyadov to the problem of population settlement clearly shows how fast the urbanization process is going in the medieval cities of Azerbaijan due to the influx of people from the villages. Therefore, in the Middle Ages, the population flow from villages to cities occurred not only in European countries, but also in Azerbaijan. If urbanization in Europe was related to the

creation of craft production, in Azerbaijan this process was related to the wide spread of highly developed multi-field artisanal industries and the great demand for labor force.

Of course, during the periods of Azerbaijan's history accompanied by wars, there were cases of sharp population decline in our medieval cities. In particular, the attacks of the Mongol troops on Azerbaijan resulted in the razing of cities to the ground, the reduction of natural and mechanical growth to a critical level: "Ar-dabil and Beylagan cities remained depopulated and devastated for 7-8 years" [1, p.57]. As a result of the merciless struggle of the Golden Horde state with the Hulagus in order to strengthen in Azerbaijan, it turned our country into a field of military operations. Of course, the severe consequences of military operations did not bypass the demographic processes. In the words of A. Alizadeh, a well-known researcher of the mentioned period: "Cities and villages were destroyed and looted, agricultural fields were trampled and destroyed, and in some cases, architectural monuments were blown up". Or we read in another century of research to show that the population in the medieval cities of Azerbaijan significantly decreased after the Mongol invasions: "According to Muhammad Nakhchivani from Nakhchivan, until the end of the XIII century, people lived in six out of every ten houses" [7, p.52].

The demographic picture of the mentioned period can also be found in the research works of Azerbaijan published at the beginning of the XXI century. In R. Mammadov's work "Northern Azerbaijani cities in the VII-XIV centuries", we read: "It was said among the people that the Mongols spread everywhere like locusts. The population paid up to forty taxes to the state and the feudal lords, and paid fees" [13, p. 288].

It is known that the level of natural growth of the population in each period is related to political stability, as well as to the production of first-class, important natural resources in the necessary amount that will be enough for livelihood and growth. The Mongols' replacement of arable land with pasture had a very negative effect on the economic and, therefore, demographic situation of the population. R. Mammadov rightly writes that thanks to the destructive activity of the nomadic Mongols, the densely populated cities of Azerbaijan declined, some of them lost their importance and turned into small settlements, and some of them completely disappeared [13, p.288].

Referring to the sources of the time, R. Huseynzadeh writes about the attacks of the Khazars in the 626-627 that the cities of Azerbaijan were sometimes in danger of disappearing or being completely destroyed as a result of the attacks of enemies in the Middle Ages: "At the end of 626, the Khazars entered Azerbaijan and advanced to Kura, taking a lot of booty: captives, goods, gold dishes, expensive clothes were seized. ...In 627, they attacked Darban and destroyed the city to its foundations, sparing neither the young, nor the woman, nor the man, nor even the old, and slaughtered them all at once" [12, p. 167].

The source cited by the author compares the attack of the Khazars to fire falling on reeds. This indicates a decrease in the natural growth rate of the population.

On the other hand, we witness the fact that the local population that survived here fled with their heads and were subjected to the process of forced migration: "After hearing the fate of Darband, the inhabitants of Caucasian Albania fled to the capital Barda, and from there to the mountains of Karabakh. However, the enemy was able to capture some of them at the foot of the mountain" [12, p. 167].

It should be noted that during the reign of Uzun Hasan, the ruler of the Aggoyunlu state, there was progress in the economic progress of Azerbaijan. Although the Aggoyunlu state was large in territory, it was not so strong economically and politically. Incessant wars had a negative impact on the country's economy. The population paid 31 types of taxes and fees. On the other hand, the strengthening of nomadic military nobles who did not want to submit to the central authority strengthened the feudal arbitrariness even more. Deprived of the necessary means of living, the population either ran away from the country or became a victim of internecine wars. It can be said that the number of newly established families is significantly decreasing, child mortality has increased. All these listed factors had a devastating effect on the demographic situation. To prevent this, Uzun Hasan prepared "Qanunname" (Legislation – A.M.), which became known as "King Hasan's Laws", precisely defined and reduced what was to be collected from the peasants, and ensured that taxes flowed directly to the treasury. Relations with European countries, especially the Republic of Venice, were significantly strengthened in order to capitalize on the silk trade, which is the country's main source of income. Uzun Hasan also invited specialists from Italy to provide his army with firearms. This once again demonstrates the concerns of the medieval rulers about the demographic situation. Regarding this and many other issues, a number of research works in Azerbaijani historiography of the beginning of the 21st century, including Y. Mahmudov (Azerbaijan's relations with European countries. Baku, ADU, 1986, 96 p.); Azerbaijani diplomacy. Baku, Tahsil, 2006, 416 p.), K. Shukurov (The population of Azerbaijan: history and sources of study (from ancient times to modern times). Baku, Elm, 2004, 974 p.), F. Abasov (Karabakh khanate. Baku, Tahsil, 2007, 278 p.), H. Gasimov (Azerbaijani culture in the Middle Ages. Baku, Aspoligraf, 2008, 448 p.), F. Bagirov (The resettlement policy of tsarism in Azerbaijan (1830-1914). Moscow, Maroseika, 2009, 704 p.), E. Alibayova's (Questions of the ancient history of Azerbaijan in Russian historiography of the 19th - early 20th centuries. Baku, Elm, 2009, 224 p.), N. Bayramova (Shamakhi Khanate. Baku, Elm, 2009, 396 p.), N. Valikhanli (Azerbaijan in VII-XII centuries: history, sources, comments. Baku, Elm ve tehsil, 2016, 480 p.), Sh. Fazil (History of Guba. Baku, TEAS Press, 2016, 700 p.) and so on.

From the cited examples, it is once again clear that the decrease or increase of the population in the medieval cities of Azerbaijan directly depended on the political events and processes taking place in the mentioned period in Azerbaijan. All these information clearly show that the medieval city planning of Azerbaijan was organized at a high level, based on scientific

knowledge, including the objective reasons for population density in medieval cities.

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